

The Chemistry of Jute-lignin. Part VI. Isolated Lignin and Lignin Native in Jute.

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It is well known that isolated lignin is different from raw lignin as regards many colour reactions. Lignin separated from jute in the usual way has a dark appearance, although jute itself is practically white. It is for this reason, that according to the varying methods of isolation, different investigators have reported different types of lignins even when the source is the same.

Wood and similar lignified materials afford acetic acid when distilled with dilute mineral acids but lignin, prepared from these raw materials, does not give any trace of the aforesaid acid, when similarly treated. Jute also has been found to behave in a similar manner and lignin prepared from it does not give any acetic acid. Delignified jute and raw jute itself have been found to give the same amount of acetic acid (*cf.* Table I).

This fact leads to the conclusion that lignin native in jute does not contain any acetyl group as is held by Heuser (*Paper Trade J.*, 1930, 83, 75). The view of Jonas (*Papier Fabrikant.*, 1928, 26, 221) that the acetyl group is split off from lignin during isolation, is not justified. The acetic acid in delignified jute has been found to be due to the pectin residue as when all the pectin was extracted with 0.5% solution of ammonium oxalate at 80°-90°, the residue no longer gave any acetic acid. This also proves that cellulose or hemicelluloses are incapable of giving acetic acid under these circumstances. That pectin gives acetic acid has been shown by several investigators (Fuchs, "Chemie des Lignins", 1926, p. 234) and our results further corroborate their observations.

Like other lignins jute-lignin contains methoxy groups. Delignified jute has been found to give methoxy from which it may be concluded that pectin residue also contains methoxy group. It has been found that half of this methoxy residue in pectin is in the form of an ester, as the methoxy figure of delignified jute after boiling with 1% KOH is half that of the untreated sample (*cf.* Table II).

HCl-lignin has been shown before by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 397) to give CO_2 when boiled with 12% HCl but no furfural. The latter fact shows that no uronic acid or pectin residue is attached to lignin. Chloro-lignin from jute and separated lignin have now been found after repeated purification from acetone and alcohol to give CO_2 even in an atmosphere of hydrogen. This suggests the presence of COOH group in lignin with a negative group in the α -position, for it is well known that such organic compounds yield CO_2 more or less readily even when boiled alone or with mineral acids. This view of the presence of COOH is supported by Rassow and Wagner (*Wochenblatt f. Papier-fabrikation*, 1932, 63, 103), who from the conductivity of Na-lignin from pinewood found the presence of three COOH groups, as also by Mehta (*Biochem. J.*, 1925, 19, 961) who determined the acid value as 477.

Determination of CO_2 was done in raw jute, delignified jute and lignin respectively in order to find out any difference in its value and also to justify the presence of CO_2 residue in lignin (*cf.* Table III).

An attempt to get an idea of the formaldehyde content of lignin, native in jute, proved futile as no suitable method was found which could be relied upon in presence of furfural.

As has already been shown by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 691), the slight discrepancy in furfural value in raw and delignified jute is due to the liberation of formaldehyde from lignin. This indirectly proves that lignin should give no furfural which has actually been found to be the case with separated jute-lignin. Hence, separated lignin is identical with the native one in this respect.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Determination of acetic acid in raw and delignified jute.—1.15 G. of the sample (of known moisture content) was boiled under reflux with 100 c.c. of KOH solution for 3-4 hours. It was filtered, washed neutral and acidified with sulphuric acid. The precipitate was filtered off and the filtrate distilled in steam; this was continued until the distillate was neutral to litmus. Acetic acid was then estimated with $N/10$ -alkali in the usual way. Blank experiments were done side by side to make a correction for sulphuric acid, which gives a little sulphurous acid on prolonged steam

distillation. 10% is the minimum strength of KOH that hydrolyses completely the acetyl group.

TABLE I.

Substance taken.	Hydrolysing agent and its strength.	Acetic acid (on dry sample).
Raw jute washed with neutral soap and made free from fat	0.5% KOH	5.89%
	1	5.82
	5	5.97
	* 10	6.29
	15	6.23
	20	6.26
	17.5% in the cold	4.73
	10% H ₂ SO ₄	4.93
Delignified jute	10% KOH	7.53
	15	7.42
	20	7.73

As jute contains 15.43% of lignin, 84.57 g. of delignified jute, therefore, give 6.26 g. of acetic acid; hence 100 g. of it would give 7.40 g. Actually 7.54 g. have been obtained from jute delignified by ClO₂, which, therefore, shows, the absence of acetyl group in lignin. Boiling of raw jute with 1% KOH for one hour for facilitating delignification was avoided for obvious reasons.

Presence of methoxy group in lignin and delignified jute and its determination.—In Zeisel's apparatus (with Perkin's modification) dimethylaniline was taken in the conical flask instead of usual alcoholic silver nitrate, other arrangements for methoxy determination remaining the same. The vapour of alkyl iodide at once formed crystalline derivatives. It was filtered, washed with CHCl₃ (in which it was but slightly soluble) and dried. It did not melt but decomposed at 220°, as also the fraction recovered from CHCl₃. The methoxy values were estimated in the usual way by Zeisel's method and the results are given in the following table.

TABLE II.

Sample	Wt	Moisture.	AgI	Methoxy (on dry sample).	Mean
Raw jute	0 4102 g	10 0 %	0·1127 g	3 98 %	3 965
	0 5778	,	0 1575	3 95	
Delignified jute (without alkali boiling)	0 6085	9 50	0 5598	1 316	1 338
	0 7162	„	0 6673	1 358	
Do (alkali boiled)	0 6220	9 61	0 0260	0 601	0 608
	0 7685	„	0 0325	0 616	
HCl-lignin (at room temp)	0 3050	Nil	0 3787	16 38	16 41
	0 2806	„	0 3496	16 44	

Jute contains 15 43% lignin (by HCl method) calculated on the dry sample, and if X be its actual methoxy content, then $15\ 43\ X/100 + (100 - 15\ 43) \times 1\ 338/100 = 3\ 965$, whence $X = 18\ 37$. The methoxy value of separated lignin being 16 41%, it appears that lignin has suffered a loss of 1 96 % of methoxy in the course of isolation. It may be pointed out here that with a mol wt of 330, and 5 methoxy groups, the value comes to 18 66 %. This value of the mol wt of lignin has been arrived at by the author by the chlorination of lignin (*J Indian Chem Soc*, 1934, 11, 777) and by the determination of its formaldehyde content (*ibid*, p 691).

Determination of CO₂ in jute, delignified jute and lignin —1 G of the sample was boiled with 100 c c of 12% HCl on a glycerine bath and the gas was passed with CO₂-free air through an upright condenser to two gas washers, each containing 100 c c of N/10 baryta for 4-5 hours. The supernatant liquid (25 c c) was titrated next day with N/10 HCl and CO₂ was calculated in the usual way. The results are shown in the following table.

TABLE III

Sample.	Wt	Moisture	N/10-baryta consumed	CO ₂ on dry sample)	Mean
Raw jute	1 2435 g	10 2 %	8 75 c c	1 86 %	1 630
	1 1522	„	9 15	1 80	
Delignified jute	1 1986	9 8	9 35	1 91	1 915
	1 2225	„	9 65	1 92	
HCl-lignin (at room temp)	1 5480	Nil	10 85	1 54	1 56
	1 8205	„	13 10	1 58	

(100—15·43) *i.e.*, 84·57 g. of delignified jute would give 1·62 g. of CO₂, whence in raw jute the deficiency due to lignin is (1·830—1·62) *i.e.*, 0·21 g. Lignin, therefore, should give 1·38% of CO₂, while actually 1·56 % have been found. This value may not represent the theoretical one, for the splitting off of CO₂ is not usually quantitative in such cases. The moisture in the above experiments was determined by heating the sample under vacuum over P₂O₅ at 110° until the weight was constant.

SUMMARY.

(1) It has been shown by an indirect method that lignin contains no acetyl groups. Isolated lignin in this respect is not different from the lignin native in jute.

(2) The absence of alkoxy groups other than methoxy in jute-lignin has been definitely established.

(3) Lignin suffers a loss of 1·96 % of methoxy during isolation by HCl in the ordinary way. The theoretical value 18·37 % agrees fairly well with the assumption that lignin has a mol. wt. of 830 and has 5 methoxy groups.

(4) The CO₂ values of raw and delignified jute indicate that lignin should give CO₂; the calculated and actual values are almost coincident.

(5) Owing to difficulties in estimation, it is not possible to say how much H·CHO lignin native in jute should give.

In conclusion, it gives me much pleasure to record here my sincere and grateful thanks to Prof. J. C. Ghosh and Dr. J. K. Chowdhury for their kind interest and valuable suggestions.

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Received July 7, 1934.
